

A P O L L O

D1.5: 4th Report on Advisory Board meetings

WP1 – Project Management

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Executive summary

The current deliverable represents the 4th Report on the Advisory Board, the final deliverable under this task and it presents an overview of the suggestions of the members of the advisory board as well as the actions that were taken to address them. In total seven members were added to the board throughout the project, in different phases, depending on their expertise. The present document summarises the recommendations that the experts had to offer, as well as the actions that were taken from the consortium to address them.

The document is structured as follows: Chapter 1 provides a recap of the role of the EEAB to the APOLLO project, in Chapter 2 the profiles of all the members are briefly presented, Chapter 3 contains the recommendations of the board and the respective actions that were taken to address them, while Chapter 4 entails the conclusions.

1 The role of the External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) in a nutshell

As previously mentioned the tasks and roles of the Advisory Board can be many. In the present we mention indicatively that some of them are to provide advice, guidance and recommendations, additional quality control and validation, feedback, extend the scientific and market potential of the project and increase the visibility of the project. In order to ensure some of the above the APOLLO advisory board was formed early on the project (M4) and it will follow it until the end of its duration.

The External Expert Advisory Board already consists of experts with world-wide reputation in their scientific and technical fields such as Earth Observation, ICT for agriculture, farm management systems, market exploitation and stakeholder collaboration and engagement. The newly invited members only add up to that, since their widely acknowledged members of their communities.

2 The EEAB members

The invitations that were extended from the beginning until the end of the project from the consortium were: i) Mrs Dr. Paula Antunes; ii) Mr. Dr. Claus Aage Grøn Sørensen; iii) Mr. Milan Miric; iv) Prof. Dr. Alexander Löw; v) Francesco Mattia; vi) Dr. Birgitte Holt Andersen; and vii) to Dr. Alexander Gruber.

In the sub-chapters below a brief profile of each of the board members and their respective expertise are presented.

2.1 Ms. Dr. Paula Antunes

Paula Antunes has a degree in Environmental Engineering (5 years) and a PhD in Environmental Systems from the Universidade Nova de Lisboa. She is Full Professor at the Department of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, where she has been a lecturer since 1982. She teaches Environmental Management, Corporate Environmental Management, Ecological Economics and Sustainability

Science both in MSc and PhD programs (Environmental Engineering MSc Program, European Master in System Dynamics and Environment PhD Program). Paula Antunes was the Head of the Department of Environmental Sciences and Engineering in the period 2006-2009 and she currently is the Director of CENSE – Center for Environmental and Sustainability Research, classified as Excellent in the scope of the Programa de Financiamento Plurianual de Unidades de I&D of the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT-MCTES). She has a background in environmental engineering and considerable experience in developing interdisciplinary research and coordinating multidisciplinary research teams in the interface between natural and social sciences. Her research interests are focused in ecological economics with an emphasis in sustainability assessment, system dynamics modelling, environmental management and methods and tools for stakeholder engagement in environmental planning and decision support. She has coordinated and participated in several research projects, financed by the European Commission and the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology. She has also participated in several studies both for public and private organizations, dealing with environmental assessment, support to the development and implementation of environmental policies, sustainability monitoring and benchmarking. She has

authored and co-authored a significant number of publications in peer reviewed journals and books and she has collaborated in several national and international expert panels. She is Associate Editor of Ecological Economics and has been Vice-President of the European Society for Ecological Economics (ESEE) between 2006-2009 and has served in the board of the International Society for Ecological Economics (ISEE) (2002-2004). She was a member of the Portuguese Council for Sustainable Development between 2009-2011 and belongs to the Scientific Council for Natural Resources and the Environment of the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology. Ms. Dr. Paula Antunes was invited to join APOLLO Advisory Board due to her expertise in policy analysis and stakeholder engagement. She was proposed by partner AgriSat.

2.2 Mr. Dr. Claus Aage Grøn Sørensen

Claus Grøn Sørensen is a Senior Scientist/Head of Research Unit in the Operations Management division of the Department of Engineering, Aarhus University, Denmark. He holds a PhD in Production and Operations Management. He has over 25 year experience in production and operations management, decision analysis, information modeling, system analysis, and simulation and modeling of technology application in agriculture. Research topics include resource analyses and optimizations, whole farm analyses and optimizations, the feasibility of introducing robotic systems in agriculture, development of management information systems and smart applications (e.g. FP7, FutureFarm, AgriFood2). He has participated (as project coordinator, WP leader, and partner coordinator) in multiple international projects. He is the author of more than 350 articles in peer reviewed Journals and conference proceedings. He is currently the Danish representative on the Executive Council of the European Society of Agricultural Engineers (EugAgEng), post-chairman for CIGR (International Commission of Agricultural Engineering) Section V on System Management, and currently the President of EurAgEng (European Society of Agricultural Engineers). Main areas of research and qualifications Production and operations management with focus on: i) Operations analyses and modeling (optimisation and evaluation of production systems and decision support logistics, supply chain management); ii) Resource analyses and optimisations (technology usage, energy demand, and work methods, Life Cycle Assessment); iii) Information modeling (information types and information flows in relation to management of systems, requirements for design of ICT systems, information valuation/value chain); iv) System analyses/system engineering (technology assessment, impact assessment of innovative technologies, sensitivity analyses/feasibility studies, simulation/modeling) Mr. Sørensen was proposed by partner Agricultural University of Athens.

2.3 Mr. Milan Miric

Mr. Milan Miric is currently the Executive Director of the Regional Development Agency of Srem Municipality, Serbia. He is responsible for the planning, management and realization of regional development projects related to local infrastructure, tourism, agriculture and energy efficiency as well as developing an annual strategy for the municipality. He has been in close liaison between the municipality, the ministries, the central government and EU agencies. Mr. Miric has a great experience in management, budget planning, strategic planning on local level, organizational development, quality and innovation management. He has a project work experience gained through more than 30 municipality projects financed from municipality budget, republic budget, EU funds, Exchange, GTZ and USAID. Mr. Miric has been proposed by partner University of Belgrade - Faculty of Civil Engineering (UBFCE) due to his extensive experience in local regional development and agriculture in Serbia.

2.4 Prof. Dr. Alexander Löw

Prof. Dr. Alexander Löw was a professor in Physical Geography and Microwave Remote Sensing at the Department for Geography at Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität Munich (LMU) since 2015.

Before joining LMU, he joined the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology, Hamburg, Germany in 2009. There he was leading a research group on Terrestrial Global Remote Sensing, focusing on global-scale remote sensing for climate studies. His research interests included the quantitative retrieval of geophysical parameters from remote sensing data, the development of image processing algorithms, coupling of land surface process models with microwave scattering and emission models, and the development of land surface process models and data assimilation techniques.

Prof. Dr. Alexander Löw also received his PhD and his habilitation at LMU, where from 2001 to 2008, during his PostDoc research, he worked on the retrieval of bio- and geophysical parameters from microwave remote sensing data. In addition Prof. Dr. Löw in 2007 was a Visiting Scientist with the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, Greenbelt, MD.

His scientific activities included his role as an editor for Hydrology and Earth System Science, as a guest editor in Nonlinear Processes in Geophysics, as reviewer for several national and international journals, as a Board Member in the Scientific Board of ESA CarbonFlux Projekt and as an associate editor for the Remote Sensing of Environment.

He served as an expert in various organisations such as: EUMETSAT, ESA, DWD CMSAF, H-SAF, Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NOW), Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- and Raumfahrt (DLR).

Indicatively we are citing below some of his peer reviewed publications, including the one used by the APOLLO project:

- Axel Lauer, Veronika Eyring, Mattia Righi, Michael Buchwitz, Pierre Defourny, Martin Evaldsson, Pierre Friedlingstein, Richard de Jeu, Gerrit de Leeuw, Alexander Loew, Christopher J. Merchant, Benjamin Müller, Thomas Popp, Maximilian Reuter, Stein Sandven, Daniel Senftleben, Martin Stengel, Michel Van Roozendaal, Sabrina Wenzel, Ulrika Willén (2017) Benchmarking CMIP5 models with a subset of ESA CCI Phase 2 data using the ESMValTool, Remote Sensing of Environment, doi:10.1016/j.rse.2017.01.007.
- Loew, A., Andersson, A., Trentmann, J., Schröder, M. (2016). Assessing Surface Solar Radiation Fluxes in the CMIP Ensembles. Journal of Climate. 29. 7231-7246. doi: 10.1175/JCLI-D-14-00503.1.
- Loew, A., Bennartz, R., Fell, F., Lattanzio, A., Doutriaux-Boucher, M., and Schulz, J.: A database of global reference sites to support validation of satellite surface albedo datasets (SAVS 1.0), Earth Syst. Sci. Data, 8, 425-438, doi:10.5194/essd-8-425-2016, 2016.
- Loew, A. et al., 2014. Do we (need to) care about canopy radiation schemes in DGVMs? Caveats and potential impacts. Biogeosciences, 11(7), pp.1873–1897. doi: 10.5194/bg-11-1873-2014
- Loew, A., Ludwig, R., Mauser, W. Derivation of surface soil moisture from ENVISAT ASAR Wide Swath and Image Mode data in agricultural areas. IEEE Trans. On Geosc. And Rem.Sens., 2006, 44(4), 889-899.

2.5 Francesco Mattia

Francesco Mattia is a senior research scientist at the Institute of Intelligent Systems for Automation (ISSIA), National Council of Research (CNR), Bari, Italy. His research field is direct and inverse modeling of microwave scattering from land surfaces. He has extensively worked on the retrieval of land biogeophysical parameters (e.g. soil moisture content, soil roughness, vegetation biomass) from Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data. More recently, his scientific interests have been steered to investigate the integrative use of earth observation data and land surface process models (e.g. hydrologic or crop growth models) for improving water and agricultural resources management.

He has been a visiting scientist at the Centre d'Etudes Spatiales de la Biosphère (CESBIO), Toulouse, France, during 1996, 1997, 1998 and 1999; at University of California Santa Barbara (USA) during 2008; and at Ohio State University (USA) during 2011. He was among the co-organizers the 5th International Workshop on "Retrieval of Bio- and Geo-Physical Parameters from SAR Data for Land Applications" held at Bari (Italy) in 2007 and a member of the Earth Science Advisory Committee of European Space Agency.

Mr. Mattia has managed various projects such as: "GMES Sentinel-1 Soil Moisture Algorithm Development", funded by European Space Agency (ESA); "Use of COSMO-SkyMed SAR data for LANDcover classification and surface parameters retrieval over agricultural sites (COSMOLAND)", funded by Italian Space Agency (ASI); "Exploiting longer wavelength SAR data for the improvement of surface process modelling", funded by ESA-ESTEC.

Indicatively we are citing below some of his journal publications:

- J. D. Ouellette, J. T. Johnson, A. Balenzano, F. Mattia, G. Satalino, S.B. Kim, R. Scott Dunbar, A. Colliander, M. H. Cosh, T. G. Caldwell, J. P. Walker, A. A. Berg: A Time-Series Approach to Estimating Soil Moisture from Vegetated Surfaces using L-band Radar Backscatter, *IEEE Trans. on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, Vol. 55, No. 6, pp. 3186-3193, 2017, DOI: 10.1109/TGRS.2017.2663768.
- G. Satalino, A. Balenzano, F. Mattia, and M. W. J. Davidson: "C-band SAR Data for Mapping Crops Dominated by Surface or Volume Scattering", *Geosci. and Remote Sensing Letters*, Vol.11, Issue 2, pp. 384-388, Feb. 2014, ISSN: 1545-598X, DOI: 10.1109/LGRS.2013.2263034
- V. Iacobellis, A. Gioia, P. Milella, G. Satalino, A. Balenzano and F. Mattia: "Inter-comparison of hydrological model simulations with time series of SAR-derived soil moisture maps", *European Jou. of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 46, pp. 739-757, 2013, ISSN: 2279-7254, DOI: 10.5721/EuJRS20134644
- Balenzano, G. Satalino, F. Lovergine, M. Rinaldi, V. Iacobellis, N. Mastronardi, F. Mattia: On the use of temporal series of L- and X-band SAR data for soil moisture retrieval. Capitanata plain case study, *European Journal of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 46, 2013
- F. Mattia: Coherent and incoherent scattering from tilled soil surfaces, *Waves in random media*, Vol. 21, 2011

2.6 Dr. Birgitte Holt Andersen

Dr. Birgitte Holt Andersen holds a PhD in Corporate Strategy and a Master's degree in Economics. She has profound experience with the European Union, working as Commission staff at the Joint Research Centre in Ispra (Space Institute) and DG TREN (Galileo Unit). She has worked intensively with projects for the European Space Agency (ESA) in relation to the GMES/ COPERNICUS (Global Monitoring for Environment and Security) Programme. Through her employment with the European Commission and later as Chief Project Manager for a large Consultancy firm, she gained experiences with European Policies from leading assignments for various EC customers in particular Regional Development Fund, European Investment Bank, General Directorate for Environment. She has participated in several European research projects as business partner responsible for economic feasibility analysis, development of relevant business models and market exploitation strategies. On a regular basis she acts as expert evaluator and reviewer of EC Research Programmes: Horizon 2020 (Space, Environment), Eurostar. Her analytical tool box includes policy impact assessment, cost benefit analysis, structural analysis of industries, value chain assessment and dynamics, competition analysis, market assessments, environmental and socio – economic analyses, life cycle cost analysis and externalities.

2.7 Alexander Gruber

Mr. Alexander Gruber received his BSc degree in Geodesy and Geoinformation, and his MSc degree in Geodesy and Geophysics, both from the Vienna University of Technology (TUW), in 2012 and 2013 respectively. Since 2013 he is working on his Ph.D. degree in remote sensing. His main research interest lies in geophysical parameter retrieval using remote sensing techniques, error characterization of earth observation data sets, up- and down-scaling techniques, and data assimilation, with a special focus on soil moisture. Mr. Gruber was a member of the APOLLO TUW team from the beginning of the project and with an integral role in the technical project implementation. In 2018 he joined KU Leuven University, where he is continuing his research. Taking into consideration his expertise and his role in the realization of the project APOLLO partners have extended an invitation to Mr. Gruber to join the APOLLO project from a different post, that of the Expert External Advisory Board. Finally, it should be mentioned that Mr. Gruber has been author and co-author of various peer-reviewed as seen below:

- L. Ciabatta, C. Massari, L. Brocca, A. Gruber, C. Reimer, S. Hahn, C. Paulik, W. Dorigo, R. Kidd, W. Wagner: "SM2RAIN-CCI: a new global long-term rainfall data set derived from ESA CCI soil moisture"; *Earth System Science Data*, 10 (2018), 267 - 280. BibTeX
- W. Dorigo, D. Chung, A. Gruber, S. Hahn, T. Mistelbauer, R. Parinussa, C. Reimer, R. van der Schalie, R. De Jeu, W. Wagner: "[Hydrological cycle] Soil Moisture [in "State of the Climate in 2016"]"; *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 98 (2017), 8; 30 - 32. BibTeX,
- W. Dorigo, W. Wagner, C. Albergel, F. Albrecht, G. Balsamo, L. Brocca, D. Chung, M. Ertl, M. Forkel, A. Gruber, E. Haas, P. Hamer, M. Hirschi, J. Ikonen, R. De Jeu, R. Kidd, Y. Liu, D. Miralles, T. Mistelbauer, N. Nicolai-Shaw, R. Parinussa, C. Pratola, C. Reimer, R. van der Schalie, S. Seneviratne, T. Smolander, P. Lecomte: "ESA CCI Soil Moisture for improved Earth system understanding: State-of-the art and future directions"; *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 203 (2017), 185 - 215. BibTeX

- A. Gruber, W. Dorigo, W. Crow, W. Wagner: "Triple Collocation-Based Merging of Satellite Soil Moisture Retrievals"; *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 55 (2017), 12; 6780 - 6792. BibTeX
- A. Loew, W. Bell, L. Brocca, C. Bulgin, J. Burdanowitz, X. Calbet, R. Donner, D. Ghent, A. Gruber, T. Kaminski, J. Kinzel, C. Klepp, J. Lambert, G. Schaepman-Strub, M. Schröder, T. Verhoelst: "Validation practices for satellite-based Earth observation data across communities"; *Reviews of Geophysics*, 55 (2017), 3; 779 - 817. BibTeX

3 Results and recommendations for APOLLO

All results and recommendations produced from the meetings with the members of the advisory board are summarized in the table below. The results and recommendations table contains the following fields: a) The name of the EEAB Member, b) the recommendation and advice that resulted from the discussion, c) the respective work package that the recommendation refers to, d) the responsible APOLLO partners that have to incorporate the recommendation, e) the respective deliverable that the recommendation has to be incorporated in, f) a time plan for implementing the recommendations and g) a field for extra comments.

It has to be noted here that all results and recommendations presented in the following table are not binding but rather indicative. They are presented in order to act as a starting point of discussions among the consortium and the EEAB members. The Coordinator in consultation with the project Executive Board and the WP leaders will decide whether these results and recommendations will be included in the project, in which format and in which deliverable.

Name	Recommendations, Suggestion and advice	WP	Partner	Deliverable	Timeplan	Comments / Actions
Paula Antunes	Get inner knowledge of policies in Serbia related to Agriculture and EO	WP2, WP6	UBFCE, UPOR	-	M14	APOLLO already includes two partners (UBFCE and UPPR) and an EEAB Member Milan Miric from Serbia who will provide the proposed consultation.

Name	Recommendations, Suggestion and advice	WP	Partner	Deliverable	Timeplan	Comments / Actions
Paula Antunes	More targeted actions needed to reach the majority of the farmers and not just the ones who participate in the pilots. Increase user engagement from the beginning of the project	WP7	EVF	D7.2, D7.6, D7.7, D7.8, D7.9	All project duration	Design of specific dissemination material, which were updated throughout the project. Participation of partners in events/ workshops from early project stages. Networking of the partners and presentation of APOLLO to various stakeholders.
Paula Antunes	Show/demonstrate the usefulness and results of the developed solution from these tools as soon as they become available.	WP6, WP7	UBFCE, AUA, EVF	D6.5, D6.6, D6.7, D7.2, D7.6, D7.7, D7.8, D7.9	All project duration and after project end	The various teams worked in close cooperation with each other in order to ensure that all progress and results were included as updates to the various materials and channels that were used to promote the project.
Paula Antunes	Reliability of provided services must be proven	WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	AUA, UBFCE, TUW, DRAXIS, Starlab	D5.2, D5.3, D6.5, D6.6, D6.7	During pilot implementation (M13M34) and after project end	The reliability of the services was indeed proven in the evaluation and validation of the results.
Paula Antunes	Reduce uptake barrier risk. Involve users from the beginning, connect tech partners with real users	WP2, WP6, WP7	AgriSat, UBFCE, EVF	D2.3, D6.5, D6.6, D6.7, D7.2, D7.6, D7.7, D7.8, D7.9	All project duration	User participation in the pilots was increased throughout the last two years and apart from alpha users, more were included and participated in the evaluation of the APOLLO.

Name	Recommendations, Suggestion and advice	WP	Partner	Deliverable	Timeplan	Comments / Actions
Paula Antunes	Try to reach and set up relations with farmers associations and cooperatives	WP2, WP7	AgriSat, UPOR, ACP, EVF	D7.2, D7.6, D7.7, D7.8, D7.9	All project duration	Two cooperatives were already partners of the consortium since the beginning of the project. Partners made sure to reach more and more farmers as the APOLLO progressed from project to product. Apart from the additional farmers that are already using the platform the partners made sure to expand their network to more cooperatives, as well as other stakeholders.
Claus Sørensen	Reduce complexity of platform	WP2, WP5	DRAXIS, AUA	D2.1, D2.2, D5.2, D5.3	From project start until release of first demonstrator	User requirements collection continued even after submission of D2.1.
Claus Sørensen	Use operation analysis and modelling methodology to assess the provided services	WP4	AUA	D4.1	Until M12	Mr. Sørensen committed to work with AUA for this purpose.
Claus Sørensen	Demonstrate the environmental benefits derived from the use of APOLLO service.	WP7	EVF	D7.2, D7.6, D7.9	During pilot implementation and during the development of the services	Environmental benefits gained from the use of the service are included in dissemination material.
Claus Sørensen	Set up a blueprint for the APOLLO system	WP5	DRAXIS	D5.1	M7	The D5.1 included a detailed description of the APOLLO system architecture and design. The system architecture was also updated in the last deliverable D5.3, which included all respective changes.

Name	Recommendations, Suggestion and advice	WP	Partner	Deliverable	Timeplan	Comments / Actions
Claus Sørensen	Special attention must be given to organic farmers as a potential user group	WP7	EVF	D7.2, D7.6, D7.7, D7.8, D7.9	All project duration	No specific dissemination material was created until the end of the project, but the organic farmers are a market considered by the partners and they will try to tap into it after the end of the project.
Milan Miric	Growing representation of organic farming in Serbia. Control system for organic products existing based on EU.	WP7	EVF, UPOR, UBFCE	D7.2, D7.6, D7.7, D7.8, D7.9	All project duration	No specific dissemination material was created until the end of the project, but the organic farmers are a market considered by the partners and they will try to tap into it after the end of the project.
Milan Miric	Small farmers are mistrustful towards innovative farm management ICT tools but consider that such an approach is necessary.	WP6, WP7	UBFCE, UPOR, EVF	D6.2, D6.3, D7.2, D7.6, D7.7, D7.8, D7.9	All project duration	Tangible results were presented to smallholder farmers in Serbia. More specifically, after the first round of evaluation farmers saw first hand the results of the APOLLO platform. That turned their mistrust into trust and they are now even more invested.
Milan Miric	Adoption of farm management ICT tools from farmers and agricultural consultants in Serbia can be increased through the demonstration of positive effects using specific examples of best practice	WP6, WP7	UBFCE, UPOR, EVF	D6.2, D6.3, D7.2, D7.6, D7.7, D7.8, D7.9	All project duration	Positive effects of APOLLO usage were demonstrated during pilot implementation and supported with the design of specific dissemination material.
Milan Miric	The application should contain very precise entry parameters in real time of the shown location in order to get applicable exit data for the user	WP5	DRAXIS	D5.2, D5.3	During platform design	This recommendation has been already taken into account during the elicitation of user requirements and is included in the system design.

Name	Recommendations, Suggestion and advice	WP	Partner	Deliverable	Timeplan	Comments / Actions
Alexander Löw	Suggested an agricultural site in Austria with quite accurate data, which may also be a complementary source of data for validation for the project	WP3	Starlab, TUW	-	-	Partners TUW and Starlab took the suggestion into consideration, but were not able to include the data.
Alexander Löw	Suggested that the resolution for his algorithm depends on the area and should be used accordingly	WP3	Starlab	-	M34	Partner Starlab has already taken that into consideration.
Alexander Löw	For APOLLO there is no need to do the retrieval in geocoding, but maybe it would help to project that information as well	WP3	Starlab	-	-	It was taken into consideration by partner Starlab, nevertheless as Mr. Löw himself mentioned it was not sure if that was worth the effort.
Alexander Löw	Mr. Löw suggested for the pre-processing to alternatively be done in snap python	WP3	Starlab	D3.2	-	Starlab team is already using Sigma 0, but it will be considered in case an alternative is required.
Alexander Löw	Mr. Löw mentioned that another colleague of the domain Mr. Mattias has developed a different process to optimize irrigation index or absolute value to decrease the uncertainty of soil moisture retrieval and suggested to look into it	WP3	DRAXIS Starlab TUW UBFCE AgriSat ACP	D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4, D3.5, D3.6	-	The partners agreed to look into it and also they would have the chance to discuss with Mr. Mattias, since he was the second member towards who an invitation was extended.
Alexander Löw	Mr. Löw suggested that in order to do the calibration we will need the services to be as accurate as possible before we use them in the pilots with the farmers	WP3	DRAXIS Starlab TUW UBFCE AgriSat ACP	-	-	Service validation from technical partners was undertaken.
Francesco Mattia	Mr. Mattia suggested that in general approaches that can be considered as empirical can provide quite rational results, but normally when the results are calibrated they change and he suggested a model calibration	WP3	Starlab	D3.2	M34	It was taken into consideration by the Starlab team.

Name	Recommendations, Suggestion and advice	WP	Partner	Deliverable	Timeplan	Comments / Actions
Francesco Mattia	Mr. Mattia also stated that in his opinion since an empirical approach was selected, it should not be applied in parcel level, but in larger areas.	WP3	DRAXIS Starlab TUW UBFCE AgriSat ACP	-	-	It was taken into consideration by the team.
Francesco Mattia	Mr. Mattia made a suggestion to try to start with the easiest cases like bare soil or wheat or barley that are more sensitive, corn seems to be a rather challenging one, especially developing corn, as well as onion. He also added that it is not recommended to calibrate corn because it loses its' sensitivity to soil moisture	WP3	Starlab	-	-	It was taken into consideration by the Starlab team.
Francesco Mattia	Mr. Mattia suggested that it may be better to go at least 100 meter and product at 40meter pixel, otherwise it is too challenging	WP3	Starlab	-	-	It was taken into consideration by the Starlab team.
Brigitte Holt Andersen	Mrs. Holt Andersen suggested to widen our target groups and in addition to farmers and consultants also try to include other stakeholders such as: crop insurers, banks, fertilizer companies, machinery companies, etc	WP7	EVF	D7.11	M34	It was taken into consideration by the EVF team.
Brigitte Holt Andersen	Mrs. Holt Andersen suggested that we should also consider markets such as the crop insurance. As she mentioned that particular market is already booming in China and the US.	WP7	EVF	-	-	It was taken into consideration by the EVF team.
Brigitte Holt Andersen	Mrs. Holt Andersen suggested that our pricing scheme should be carefully considered. She mentioned that no matter what will be chosen, a recording of what the competition is doing should also be included.	WP7	EVF	D7.11	M34	It was taken into consideration by the EVF team.

Table 1 - Indicative results and recommendations table

4 Conclusions

The APOLLO consortium was in close collaboration with the External Experts Advisory Board (EEAB) members, who were constantly informed about the progress of the project and were contacted whenever a consultation from partners was needed. The current document presents the activities that were organized with the APOLLO EEAB, the feedback acquired from the experts, and the actions that the APOLLO consortium took (or plan to take) to address these recommendations. The advice that the EEAB members shared with the project partners, even though it was not binding, it was important for the progress of the project and their recommendations helped to the successful completion of the project.

5 ANNEX I – Updated APOLLO EEAB List

Name	Country	Organisation	Expertise	Proposed by
Paula Antunes	Portugal	Universidade Nova de Lisboa	Policy analysis, Stakeholder engagement	AgriSat
Claus Aage Grøn Sørensen	Denmark	Aarhus University	Operations analyses and modelling, Information modeling	AUA
Milan Miric	Serbia	Regional Development Agency of Srem Municipality	Local regional development	UBFCE
Prof. Dr. Alexander Löw	Germany	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität Munich	Terrestrial Remote Sensing* ¹	Starlab
Francesco Mattia	Italy	Institute of Intelligent Systems for Automation	Modeling of microwave scattering from land surfaces	TUW
Mrs. Birgitte Holt Andersen	Denmark	Partner Applied Economics	Business expert	Reviewer Nina Costa

¹ His research interests also include the quantitative retrieval of geophysical parameters from remote sensing data, the development of image processing algorithms, coupling of land surface process models with microwave scattering and emission models, and the development of land surface process models and data assimilation techniques

6 ANNEX II – Updated Invitation Letter

Invitation to participate in the APOLLO project External Expert Advisory Board

Thessaloniki, 2017

Dear,

We would like to invite you to become a member of the External Expert Advisory Board of the **APOLLO** project. APOLLO has received funding from the EC under the **Horizon 2020** Research and Innovation programme, which is the financial instrument of the EC that will offer funding to research projects for 7 years (2014 to 2020).

The project APOLLO (*Advisory platform for small farms based on earth observation*) aims to develop a **commercial platform** that will provide a suite of **farm management advisory services** (tillage scheduling, irrigation scheduling, crop growth monitoring, and crop yield estimation) specifically designed to address the needs of **small farmers**. APOLLO will use **state-of-the-art methodologies** for the calculation of **agricultural parameters** based on **EO data** and take advantage of the **improved spatial and temporal coverage** of the new **Sentinel satellites**.

The role of the members of the APOLLO External Expert Advisory Board is to **participate in project's meetings**, in which they will review the project activities and outcomes, identify the strong/weak points with respect to the objectives of the project and the applications of the results, and provide expert recommendations. **All travel and accommodation costs will be covered by the project budget.**

The APOLLO External Expert Advisory Board will be convened some times throughout the duration of the project either in **meetings** or in **conference calls**. With your collaboration we will be able to issue recommendations that will ensure the fulfillment of the project's objectives.

We are looking forward to welcoming you as a member of this unique group. Do not hesitate to contact us for any further information or clarification.

Best regards,

Machi Simeonidou
APOLLO Project Coordinator
DRAXIS Environmental S.A.

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This project is co-funded by the European Union

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